

Questionnaire

Innovation Performance						
No	Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
IP1	We can develop service products quickly					
IP2	We can launch the product on time					
IP3	We have a higher quality digital solution than existing products.					
IP4	We have better digital features/solutions than existing products.					

IP5	The digital product/solution application that we develop is very different from existing products.					
IP6	The products/services we develop use a different platform from existing products/services					
IP7	The products/services we develop have the novelty of digital solutions when they are launched to the market					

Open Innovation						
No	Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
	Breadth					
	Breadth of search					
IOI1	We seek to source ideas and technological information from a wide range of external sources, including conferences, the internet, journals, universities, suppliers, customers, and public and private research organizations					
	Acquiring technology					
IOI2	We seek to acquire a wide range of technologies through joint R&D, patent acquisition, licensing, joint ventures, and acquisitions.					
	Breadth of Utilization					
IOI3	We seek to leverage a wide range of external organizational partners, such as large corporations, other startups, universities, governments, etc.					
	Depth					

	Depth of search					
IOI4	We aim to leverage ideas and technological information obtained from external sources for our internal innovation process					
	Technology Development					

IOI5	We aim to leverage a wide range of external sources to develop our technology. For example, universities, public and private research organizations, large corporations, other startups, and foreign organizations.					
	Depth of Utilization					
IOI6	We aim to frequently utilize the facilities of each external organization.					

Relational capital						
No	Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
RCI1	We have networking opportunities with mentors, coaches, and incubator management staff. (RCI1)					
RCI2	We have the opportunity to share resources with other startups in the incubator. (RCI2)					
RCI3	We receive referrals from our incubator to other teams or startups within the incubator (RCI3).					
RCI4	We have opportunities to exchange knowledge and internalize it (RCI4)					
RCI5	Our incubator/accelerator program connects us with other startups within the incubator. (RCI5)					
RCE6	Our incubator/accelerator has strong relationships with other institutions, research facilities, R&D laboratories, and other facilities. (RCE6)					
RCE7	Our incubator/accelerator has access to suppliers or customers that we will target. (RCE7)					

Structure embeddedness						
No	Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
SE1	Our incubator/accelerator has close ties with innovation network centers.					
SE2	Our incubator/accelerator is located within the innovation network.					
SE3	Our incubator/accelerator has many connections and is at the center of the innovation network.					
SE4	Our incubator/accelerator has many connections to other innovators					
SE5	There are several interactions among our incubator's innovation partners.					
SE6	We easily reach other innovators through our incubator.					
SE7	Our incubator/accelerator serves as a link to other innovators and networks.					